

Non-conventional theory of oncogenesis or human cancers[†]

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Abstract : True explanations or reasons for oncogenesis or human cancers are still illusive though a number of theories have been advanced but cancer has become an undeterred menace. There is no specific oncogenic virus as such which can account for all types of cancer and probably cancer is not a virus related diseases but viruses act as secondary reason in 15–20% cases of cancer.

An attempt has been made to provide an alternative non-conventional theory of ‘oncogenesis’ based on

- (i) Water and its structural modifications leading to structural destruction or structural changes in proteins DNA, RNA etc.
- (ii) Oncogenic spots or sites and oncogenic compounds.
- (iii) Virus and virus related infections.
- (iv) Enhanced microbial activities of eukaryotes and particularly of aggressive prokaryotes and human microbiomics.

It is to be noted that the ‘seeds’ of oncogenesis are unknowingly in human biosystem. These seeds or microbes perform their specific biologic and metabolic activities in human biosystems but become aggressive due to extraneous aberrations in human body to cause cancer.

Keywords : Cancer, non-conventional method, water, virus, oncogenic sites, oncogenic compounds, microbes.

Introduction

Cancer is a complex multifactorial, multidimensional and multistep non-conventional abnormal metabolic disorder in animal and human body systems arising from hundreds of different diseases or causes and associated with metabolic malfunctions in the system.

It is characterized by uncontrolled cellular growth associated with the property of metastasis or secondary growth to invade adjacent tissues with aggressive propensity and transference of parasitic growth from one part of the body to another (by blood, lymph or by other means) affecting various physiologic and bio-physico-chemical aspects like metabolism, cell degradation, mutation etc.¹⁻³.

The uncontrolled growth develops cell masses called neoplasms or tumors (neoplasms or new growth).

According to Willis¹ ‘a tumor is an abnormal mass of tissue the growth of which exceeds and it is uncoordi-

nated with that of normal tissue and persists in the same excessive manner after the cessation of stimuli which evoked the change’.

Neoplasms or tumors are of two types :

- (1) Benign tumors i.e. mass of cells capable of limited growth and are encapsulated (remains localized in the tissue of origin).
- (2) Malignant (virulent) tumors are non-encapsulated mass of cells with irreversible growth. They infiltrate rapidly i.e. invade and kill adjacent tissues as well as distant tissues i.e. they metastasize and kill the host.

Malignant transformations, obviously the result of mutation in the cellular genome, have been supposed to be induced by agents like :

- (1) Oncogenic agents i.e. chemical carcinogens.
- (2) Oncogenic viruses.
- (3) Ionizing radiations.

[†]The paper is dedicated to the memory of my elder brother Late Professor Samir Chandra Lahiri who died from brain cancer (glioma) and all cancer patients of the world.

It has been suggested that there exist a large number of proto-oncogenes (more than 40) which are activated to oncogenes to cause cancer. The genetic mechanisms associated with the activation include :

- (i) Point mutation, deletion or insertion.
- (ii) Chromosomal translocation that relocate proto oncogene to a new chromosomal site that leads to higher expression.
- (iii) Fusion between a proto-oncogene and a second gene that produces a protein with oncogenic activity⁴⁻⁶.

Extensive and intensive studies on different aspects of carcinogenesis, its origin propagation and remediation had been made. Studies have still been pursued vigorously with advanced knowledge and diagnostic tools with money, material, manpower and vast experiences.

In spite of advancement and attainments, the real understanding of the origin and propagation of the complex multifactorial, abnormal disease called "cancer" may be considered to be inadequate. It is desirable to examine the problem of carcinogenesis from different angles to unlock the mysteries of cancer formation and to supplement the ongoing research.

It is an attempt on the part of a physical chemist to examine the genesis of cancer in human body and present a non-conventional theory of cancer formation based on the structural aspects of water, the role of microbes and human microbiomics together with aspects like oncogenic active sites, oncogenic substances and oncogenic viruses. Some of these aspects had not been properly examined.

Water is an integral part of our body and many of the diseases are directly or indirectly related to water. Water together with microbes probably play important roles in cancer formation and its development.

Naturally, it is desirable to have a brief introduction on the following :

- (1) Water and its role in biological systems.
- (2) Oncogenic or pro oncogenic substances and oncogenic active sites.
- (3) Viruses and the oncogenic viruses.
- (4) Microbes (prokaryotes and eukaryotes), their functions and human microbiomics.

Theories

1. Water and its role in biological systems¹⁻⁴⁴

Water, the most abundant biologic proactive solvent has great impact on the physiological properties of biomolecules due to its hydrogen bonding capability.

"Significance of hydrogen bond for physiology is greater than that of any other structural feature" (Linus Pauling).

Water, though benevolent, but its structures and functions are complex and probably more complicated compared to the origin and propagation of cancers.

The role of water in various diseases and drug actions has been little understood though the importance and involvement of water in life process (like water therapy) were extensively used in India from time immemorial as

"Water is the source of all life" (Thales of Miletus, 634-546 B.C.).

In an adult body system, there are approximately 1.5 kg of inorganic matter, 20% organic matter containing approximately 10% C, about 6-7% N, rest 60-70% water i.e. water is most abundant constituent. Life or biochemistry is commonly categorized as C-based but manifold biological properties (known or mostly unknown) show that life is water based or water and C-based¹⁰⁻¹⁵.

"Water is water, hydrogen two parts, oxygen one part but there is a third thing that makes it water and nobody knows what it is (D. H. Lawrence, 1885-1930)."

Water is invariably involved in all life processes. Water content of the body varies from infants (high in terms of percentage weight) to adults (low). Water is distributed between cells [intracellular fluid (ICF) ~59% (26 L) in a 75 kg man and 61% (~19 L) in 60 kg woman] and extracellular fluid (ECF) 41% (~18 L) (including ~3 L plasma) in man and ~12 L in woman⁷.

There is free movement of water between ICF and ECF, controlled by viscosity, hydrostatic and osmotic pressures and other physical properties associated with presence of ions, biomolecules etc. Structure and properties of water are considerably changed or modified by non-ionic and ionic kosmotropes and chaotropes.

Unique properties of small water molecules with flexible H-bonding capability and its chameleonic nature seems

to fit ideally into the requirement of life.

“The molecular structure of water is the essence of all life” and water is called “the matrix of life” (A. Szent Gyorgi)¹⁸.

Any disturbance in water content and its structure will lead to extreme repercussions (like water retention or water dehydration) in our body systems.

Water appears to be the missing link for many biological disorders causing multiple diseases. There is enormous void regarding the anomalous properties and structure of water and its role in physico-chemical and biologic interactions though

“We live by the grace of water” (National Geographic, special edition, November 1993)⁷.

Water and oxygen are two key compounds for all life processes. Water, the most abundant proactive solvent, is the main contributor for different molecular, metabolic and other biological reactions and interactions. It is a separating medium to transport ions, foods in acceptable forms. Water carries and distributes nutrients, metabolites, hormones, important minerals and materials throughout the macro environments and numerous micro environments of the body and within its numerous cells to perform specific biologic or physiologic functions e.g. bio-interactions in all human bodies e.g. excretion of waste products via urine and feces.

Bio-interactions are extremely complex, H-bonding is particularly important to control the activities of the biological world due to interplay of self-associating and directional properties of water and hydrophobic properties of biomolecular macro molecules like proteins, DNA, RNA, polysaccharides etc. Due to anisotropic, unbalanced properties of water associated with co-operativity, coplanarity, H-bonding ability, water interacts with hydrophobic moieties of biomolecules like protein, DNA, RNA and orients them. But the anomalous properties of water and its interactions with proteins, DNA, RNA are very little understood. These are the reasons for poor understanding of drug-receptor interactions. Water plays an important role in correct foldings of protein and the maintenance of their structures, i.e. the process by which each protein acquires or reverts to a functionally effective unique 3D-shape inspite of numerous possible folding configurations. The driving forces are the hydrophobic interac-

tions between water and protein molecules and hydrogen bonding ability^{7,8,10,15}.

As a result, proteins, DNA, RNA and other biomolecules, fold, assume shape, assemble. DNA forms helices able to zip and unzip. Enzymes possess their 3D structures and biocatalytic activities due to its H-bonding ability and collective behavior of water molecules. Aggregation of biomolecules, biocatalytic activities of enzymes and delimited cellular activity are possible only with H₂O as solvent. Water facilitates desired structural changes in macro molecules like proteins and nucleic acids, acts as a structure former maintaining cellular shape. Any disruption of the ordered arrangements and self assembly of water will lead to structural disorders in different microbiological environments in our body system which must be responsible for different diseases along with other factors. The structural changes in proteins, DNA, RNA etc. can be both reversible and irreversible. The disease that occurs due to reversible interactions between biomolecules like DNA, RNA etc. and water can be restored with time or by suitable measures like using medicines but irreversible interactions are not curable or may be virulent^{7,8,10,15}.

1.1. Water and human body^{7,8,16-29} :

Human body is an integrated system of different organs and micro environments each of specific activities and water is associated with every micro environment and its activities. Water acts on human body (or in any biological system) in a number of ways :

- (i) as thermoregulator and in forming mucous,
- (ii) as a lubricant between bodily structures and
- (iii) as a protective shock absorber for the brain and other bodies.

Other roles of water in human body :

- (i) Water molecules are the integral part for the structure and biological function of a dimeric haemoglobin¹⁹.
- (ii) Ordered water molecules with strong H-bonding facilitates (a) both proton transfer and electron transfer processes due to rapidity of connections between proton donor to acceptor sites or electron donor to electron acceptor sites²⁶ and (b) in guiding protein folding and in the protein struc-

tural prediction studies and hydration associated activity of enzymes²⁵.

1.2. Water in protein recognition and binding^{7,26-28,31-34} :

Water molecules form an integral part of most protein-protein²⁶, protein-DNA²⁷ and protein-ligand²⁸ interactions aiding the mutual recognition and both the binding thermodynamics and binding kinetics²⁹. The energetic optimization of mutual H-bonded networks between protein-water and ligand is an integral part of molecular recognition processes in enzymes, binding proteins and biological macromolecules. Water is more ordered under physiological conditions inside the cells which promotes both the protein folding rate and the stability of protein folders.

1.3. Processing of genetic information^{7,30,31} :

The processing of genetic information with DNA is facilitated by highly discriminating and strong protein-water bonding. The interfacial water molecules can serve as hydrogen fingerprints of a DNA sequence. Water takes active part in genetic signaling and transduction.

1.4. Nucleic acid hydration^{7,31} :

Conformations and utility of nucleic acid with their high ionic characters are crucially dependent on hydration. The strength of these aqueous interactions is far greater than those of proteins. Different conformations of DNA double helix are due to different hydration patterns. B-DNA, the predominant natural DNA, has a wide and deep major groove and a narrow deep minor groove, requires greatest hydration (about 30% by weight of water) to maintain the native configuration in the crystalline state. Hydration of DNA molecules appears to be different at different points and particularly stronger near the O-atoms of phosphate group.

Hydration patterns definitely vary with different configurations and their interactions with other molecules and the hydrogen pattern near the major groove and minor groove usually show sharp changes.

1.5. Hydration and dehydration :

Both hydration and dehydration affects the physiology and biochemistry of living systems.

Hydration changes the osmolarity of blood (around

284 mOsmol/kg) causing anomalous behavior. Dehydration (2–3% loss by weight) causes tiredness, headache, decreased alertness and greater dehydration may lead to collapse or even death. Both hydration and dehydration may cause kidney damage, eventual kidney failure and death.

1.6. Chaotropes and kosmotropes^{7,40-42} :

Kosmotropes and chaotropes can be both ionic and non-ionic in nature. Originally the terms kosmotropes (order maker) and chaotrope (disorder maker) denoted solutes that stabilized or destabilized proteins and membranes respectively. The terms actually referred to increasing or decreasing the structuring of water or structure making or structure breaking ions. The behavior of kosmotropes (both for non-ionic and ionic) is exactly opposite to those of chaotropes.

Chaotropes/kosmotropes unfold/fold proteins, destabilize/stabilize hydrophobic aggregates in solution and increase/reduce the solubility of hydrophobes.

Non-ionic kosmotropes stabilize protein molecules to prevent denaturation process and are divided into

- (i) Polyhydroxy compounds, well-entrenched with H-bonding arrangements.
- (ii) Zwitter-ions with weak interactions to surrounding water molecules. Here the balancing between hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity, anionic and cationic characteristics ensures good stability. They lead to the dehydration of protein surfaces, they are thermally stable but less flexible and less enzymatically active.
- (iii) Non-ionic chaotropes breakdown the H-bonded network of water i.e. decrease the order of water, increase its surface tension and destabilize macromolecular structure allowing macromolecules more structural freedom and encourage protein extension and denaturation.

Ionic kosmotropes and chaotropes :

Structure of water is considerably modified by ions depending on their charge density and on the relative strengths of ion-water interactions and water-water interactions. Ionic chaotropes and kosmotropes are divided in the way given below depending on their characteristic properties.

Ionic chaotropes	Ionic kosmotropes
Weak ion-water interactions, high H ₂ O-H ₂ O interactions. High H-bonding capabilities.	Strong ion-water interactions, low H ₂ O-H ₂ O interactions. Low H-bonding capabilities.
Strongly charged ions with low charge density.	Small or multiply charged ions with high charge density
Examples : SCN ⁻ , HSO ₄ ⁻ , HCO ₃ ⁻ , I ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺ , K ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , Cs ⁺ etc.	capable of breaking H ₂ O-H ₂ O bonds. Examples : SO ₄ ²⁻ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Li ⁺ , Na ⁺ , H ⁺ , OH ⁻ .

Biologically important ions like K⁺ and Na⁺ lie on opposite sides of the chaotropic/kosmotropic divide essential for various cellular functions. Ionic combinations in ICF and ECF are :

Ions	Intracellular fluid (ICF)	Extracellular fluid (ECF)	Nature of water
Ca ²⁺	0.1 uM	2.5 mM	High density water (HDW)
Na ⁺	10 mM	150 mM	HDW
K ⁺	159 mM	4 mM	Low density water (LDW)

Kosmotropic ions like Na⁺, H⁺, Li⁺ due to their strong ion-water interactions breaks H₂O-H₂O bonds and prefer high density water structures whereas chaotropic K⁺, NH₄⁺ ions have little interactions with H₂O-H₂O bonds and H-bonding remains undisturbed and form low density water environment : Restricted diffusion and presence of intercellular low density water structuring with high concentrations of chaotropic inorganic ions and kosmotropic other solutes within cells give different characteristics of the intercellular environment. Any tilt in the hydrogen bonding character, will change not only the kosmotropic/chaotropic character of ions but also change the physico-chemical properties like solubility of O₂, CO₂ viscosity diffusivity, pK_w and metabolic protein denaturation properties.

Water not only controls the chemistry or biochemistry and physiology of the body systems but also controls many diseases. It is clear that the biological implications of water are enormous and had not been or could not be properly evaluated. Very little is known regarding the causative and curative roles of water in diseases. However, any disease is accompanied by structural changes between water and disease causative enzymes of the etiological agents. The diseases may be curable (reversible)

in most cases and incurable (irreversible) in extreme cases. In reversible cases self repairing mechanism causes the bio system (water + biomolecules) to revert to their original configurations but in case of malignant diseases like cancer there must be destruction of water structure and water biomolecular (like proteins, DNA, RNA) configurations. The reactions must be irreversible to be repaired by usual healing mechanisms.

Moreover chaotropic and kosmotropic (both ionic and nonpolar biomolecules) characters of molecules associated with structural order or disorder of water molecules is responsible for the changes in ICF and ECF resulting in the malfunctioning of the disorganized cellular process and change in the cell membrane potential. Blood pressure may change causing heart attack or stroke or other diseases. It is to be noted that intracellular water is far more structured than extra cellular or pure water. It has been noted that the amount of “Free” versus “bound” water, K⁺ and the cytoskeleton are all linked in the differences between normal and cancer cells⁴³.

Transmembrane electrical potential is always associated with all cells. A negative variable potential ranging from -10 mV to -80 mV exists between the microelectrodes placed inside the cell (cytosol) and outside the cell due to ion-imbalances. It is known ICF inside the cytosol contains high concentrations of K⁺ ion and low concentrations of Na⁺ ion, the reverse is true for ECF. The negative charge inside the cell is due to the presence of protein anions in the cytosol which are not counter balanced by cations. The buildup of negative charge prevents the loss of more K⁺ ion and equilibrium is reached. The cell becomes polarized and trans-membrane potential (resting potential) is stabilized. Depolarization (or action potential) is developed due to endogenous or exogenous factors leading to ion imbalances between transmembrane⁴⁴.

It is well known that ultimate end of any killer disease is heart failure associated with drastic changes in ICF and ECF with change in cell membrane potentials.

Thus, instead of routine tests of blood it is desirable to measure both ionic and particularly nonionic constituents present in blood samples (associated with different diseases) using ICP/MS, HPLC, LC/MS/MS, PCA with other instruments.

2. Oncogenic sites

Oncogenic sites produced in a body (i.e. a biological system) may be inherent or developed due to metabolic malfunctions or due to multiple reasons and sites may be enriched by oncogenic compounds. Cancer whether virus infected or not require an oncogenic site in the body, an important criteria for carcinogenesis.

Creation of oncogenic spots may be due to :

- (i) Injury or lesions due to unsuccessful surgical operations or due to post-operative defects or for other reasons.
- (ii) Ulcerations in different parts of the body like duodenum, colon, alimentary tracts etc. mainly due to prolonged hyperacidity, some of the reasons may be :
 - (a) Prolonged indigestion and bacillary or enteric dysenteries, chronic amebiasis (*E. histolytica*, the etiological agent for amebiasis secretes serotonin which releases enormous amount of acids).
 - (b) Excessive use of spicy foods and toxic anti-inflammatory drugs without proper precautions.
 - (c) Over work, insomnia, mental stress and strain.
- (iii) Inflammation of epithelial tissues leading to epithelioma.
- (iv) Bruised ulcerous respiratory tracts or throat or inflammation of oesophagus.
- (v) Pancreatitis (lipase, amylase levels in urine or blood are indicators of pancreatic functions).
- (vi) Internal haemorrhages due to high blood pressure (causes of strokes and heart attacks) or due to injuries.

Haemorrhages are responsible for :

- (a) Haematoma.
- (b) Haemorrhagic clots in brain due to thrombosis and in different parts of encephalon like thromboanglitis (clot formation within an 'inflamed' vessel, may be obliterative), thromboarteritis (clot formation due to inflammation of artery), thrombocythaemia (clotting of blood vessels due to increase in platelets), thromboendartitis

(inflammation of inner lining of artery with clot formation).

There are innumerable reasons for clot formation known to medical specialists. It is to be noted that the brain or central nervous system (CNS) contains neurons (specialized cells that trigger and conduct bioelectric impulses and communications) and biosynthetically active four types (astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, microglial and ependymal) glial cells. Glial cells are primary source of brain tumors (glioma) and very active in cellular division but do not show secondary growth after injury.

Astrocytes are generally encountered source of brain tumor giving rise to astrocytomas and deadly glioblastoma multiforma⁴⁴.

It is apparent that the origin of most of the cancerous growth is in the inner parts of human body and cannot be detected or realized at early stages i.e. development of cancer is silent in most cases.

The term 'oncogenic compounds' is to some extent relative. A compound may not be oncogenic but may turn to be oncogenic depending on environmental or other biologic conditions.

The list of oncogenic or pro oncogenic compounds is exhaustive. Evidences or inferences are more indirect and statistical rather than from proper or actual experimental results. Proper statistical analysis taking one or more parameters are usually done but in living human organisms the number of parameters are not only enormous but highly variable and cancer is a multistep and multifactorial disease.

A brief survey on established oncogenic compounds with possible reasons for oncogenesis is presented.

Alcohol :

Alcohol in low dosages is not harmful as it helps to scavenge (to some extent) water insoluble toxic substances from the body. However, excess intake of alcohol is detrimental as it :

(a) Affects and destroys totally or partially the microbial flora (in stomach) responsible for carrying vital enzymic actions and metabolic functions for sustaining the living systems.

(b) Dissolves and excretes not only undesirable toxic compounds but useful compounds as well.

(c) Destroys stomach wall (composed of four coats, serous, muscular, submucous and mucous membranes), may cause perforations, ulcerations i.e. vulnerable sites for cancer.

(d) Alcoholism may cause damage or degenerative changes in liver called cirrhosis of liver.

However, damage to liver cells due to virus, microbes, toxic substances or dietary deficiencies interfering with the nutrition of liver cells may cause cirrhosis of liver.

Excess alcohol may cause the destruction of most stable tetrahedral structure of water associated with changes in the structure of biomolecules like proteins, DNA, RNA.

Pro-oncogenic (would be converted to oncogens under suitable condition) or oncogenic smoking and non-smoking tobacco products⁴⁵⁻⁵⁹

Both smoking and non-smoking tobacco products are health hazards and shorten the life span due to heart diseases and cancer in lungs, oral cavities, larynx, oesophagus, bladder, kidney, pancreas etc. Smoke from tobacco and smokeless tobacco contain a large number of compounds (shown to be 3900) including high molecular weight polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) like naphthalene, acenaphthalene, acenaphthene, fluorene, phenanthrene, fluoranthrene, benzo(α)pyrene (BAP-carcinogenic bio-indicator), chrysene, benzo(α , p)anthracene, benzo(α , p , i)perylene, terpenes, phytosterols, pesticides in addition to nicotine and its metabolite cotinine. Other chemicals of interest are CO, HCN, butadiene, benzene, acrolein, aromatic amines like 4-aminobiphenyl, 2-naphthylamine, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, catechol, nitromethane, acetonitrile, ethylenecarbamate, cadmium, polonium-240, tobacco specific nitrosamines (carcinogenic), 4-(methylnitrosamine-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK), N-nitrosornicotine (NNN), 4-(methyl-nitrosamine)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanol (NNAL) and its metabolite NNAL-glucuronide are most important.

Most of these compounds are highly toxic and water insoluble. According to Hausen⁶⁷, tobacco products are the most important risk factor and even precedes cancer virus.

There has been always attempts to increase the efficacy of tested (mostly water insoluble) drugs by increas-

ing their bioavailability i.e. increasing the lipophilic character of drugs by proper modification of -H, -OH, -COOH groups of the drugs by alkyl, aryl, acetyl groups or in other possible ways.

Tobacco products and all these synthetic drugs are water insoluble and their excretion is difficult resulting in the accumulation of toxic substances in different parts of the biological system.

They form toxic depots or active sites in between the membranes, glands, fat depots and in other vulnerable sites like ulcers, scars or lesions, haemorrhagic spots in body. Due to mass effect, they attract similar or other molecules and store them in these active depots causing swellings or tumors which may be encapsulated or which may cause perforations in the membranes or cell walls of the active depots. The hydrocarbons or other lipid soluble compounds are likely to disturb the water structure in the micro environment due to hydrophobic interactions. But the compounds serve as rich foods for microbes or etiological agents of various diseases.

3. Virus and oncogenic virus⁶⁰⁻⁶⁴

Virus (discovered by Iwanovski in 1892) is a group of pathogenic causative agent capable of passing through bacterial filters. The virus particle is a nucleocapsid containing a nucleic acid and a protein coat (may be naked or enclosed by a membrane).

Virus is a dependent organism characterized by one kind of nucleic acid either double stranded DNA or (single or double stranded) RNA necessary for reproduction and multiplication which occurs only within the host cell causing death to the host cell. Virus destroys whole cell complexes producing tissue damage, necrotic areas and lytic halos. Viruses are host specific as well as tissue or cell specific and named as neurotrophic, lymphotropic, myxotropic depending on their development in nerve cell, lymphocytes, epithelial cells or mucous membranes.

Small pox, chicken pox, rabies, poliomyelitis, influenza, the common cold, flu etc. are some virus induced diseases transmitted by direct contact or via insects.

Viral diseases in general have a brief incubation period before their outbreak. Bacteriophages (evinced from appearance of plaques or lytic halos) are produced by viruses using bacterial cells as hosts.

Virus induced diseases may turn virulent and destructive and cause epidemic. But virus infected diseases appear to be short lived and can be contained with proper care and medicine, vaccination. Virus is half genome. It has limited capacity of destruction.

Viruses that produce tumors in their natural host or in experimental materials and induce malignant transformations of cells on culture are known as oncogenic virus. Transformation (complete or partial) of normal cells to malignant cell is a multistep process like transformation, transduction, conjugation and cell-cell fusion.

Oncogenic viruses (mostly DNA viruses of different classes and one family of RNA retro virus) are classified according to nucleic acid content of genome causing mutation like changes in host cell by transformation.

For oncogenic DNA viruses, DNA is integrated with the host cell genome as prophage with rearrangements or deletions. They have multilayered growth (on top of each other) when a host cell is infected by virus or cancer infected cell. They usually proliferate only until they make contact with each other i.e. contact inhibition occurs only to have a single layer of confluent or multilayered growth.

Oncogenic DNA viruses are :

- (1) Papovaviridae (papilloma, polyoma, SV40, BK and JC).
- (2) Pox virus (molluscum, contagiosum, Shope fibroma, yabavirus).
- (3) Adenoviridae (types 2, 5, 12).
- (4) Herpesviridae (Herpes simplex types (H2), cytomegalo virus, Epstein Barr virus).
- (5) Hepadnaviridae (Hepatitis B), Blaviviride (Hepatitis C).

RNA viruses (Human T cell leukemia HTLV-I,II other viruses affecting animals).

It is apparent that those viruses have been indirectly related to carcinogenesis.

But usually 15–20% oncogenesis may be due to virus.

Thus, oncogenesis cannot be considered to be a virus related diseases, some more complicated subtle unknown causes must be the reasons.

Cancer is not a contiguous or infectious disease. There is no specific oncogenic virus as such which is responsible for all types of cancer. Cancer in fact, is a combina-

tion of hundreds of diseases and the reasons must be numerous and cannot be accounted for by a specific virus.

The development of cancer is usually in the interior regions of the human bodies and cannot be detected easily unless manifested outwardly i.e. the development of cancer is silent with a relatively long but undetermined incubation period. But cancer if detected at the early stages or in its infancy can be cured with proper treatment, care and precautions.

However, there appears to be a similarity in case of excision of phage DNA of virus and phage DNA of the cancer cells. Phage DNA virus reverts to the vegetative state by excision. It regains its autonomy and multiply inside the bacterial cell like a virulent phage. The excision thus leads to the lysis of the host cell. In case of excision surgery of cancer patients (except in the initial stage i.e. in absence of metastasis) the cells revert to the vegetative states and regain their autonomy. Rapid multiplication of cancer cells inside the affected system occurs after an initial pause like virulent phage. The surgery or excision process leads to the rapid lysis of the host cells.

4. Ecology of microorganisms and human microbiomics⁶⁰⁻⁶⁶

In spite of extensive knowledge of molecular details and different biological interactions, enormous void still exists in our knowledge of molecular biochemistry. Microbes or microbiological processes, regarded as links between plant kingdom, animal kingdom and soil kingdom (or earth) with their inherent characteristics and limitations, form the basic foundations of all living organisms like plants, animals including human beings.

Microbes with different cellular structures and non-cellular structures can be divided into⁶⁰ :

- (a) Prokaryotes – the relies from the earliest times of biological evolution.
- (b) Eukaryotes – (represents greatest discontinuity in the evolution of living organisms). These are microbes with different cellular structure. Evolution of eukaryotes occurred only after cyanobacteria provided oxygen containing atmosphere.
- (c) Virus (non-cellular particles incapable of self-replication).

All these microbes are necessarily involved in most of the diseases.

Most of the biological processes owe much to microorganisms because of their rapid growth, extensive adaptability and ease of multiplication and manipulations. Bacteria and cyanobacteria are ubiquitous in nature. Microbes are omnipresent, only the environment or habitat determines which species should survive, reproduce and perform their activity. Metabolic flexibility in microorganisms are extremely high and extensive adaptability is due to their small size.

Detailed microbial aspects are the subject matter of text books on microbiology⁶⁰⁻⁶⁴.

However, a very brief description of prokaryotes and eukaryotes are presented as a part of objective to present a non-conventional theory of carcinogenesis or cancer formation.

Prokaryotes and eukaryotes have fundamental differences in genome size, constitutional aspects, functions, structure of nucleus and the type of nuclear division.

Prokaryotes usually anoxic in nature, developed on their own long and long ago whereas eukaryotes oxic in nature developed only after availability of sufficient amount of oxygen.

Prokaryotes have small cell and genome sizes and contain nuclear region as very fine threads bordering directly on cytoplasm consisting of a large number of ribosomes of 70s type⁶⁰. Cytoplasmic membrane is the site of respiratory and photosynthetic energy generation. Entire genetic information of the prokaryotes is contained in a single thread of DNA, the bacterial chromosomes, with circular strands without histones. Simple cell structure, high growth rate, well developed regulatory systems and the multiple mechanism of gene transfer of prokaryotes are probably the reasons of development of their metabolic and physiological diversity.

Small genome and haploid nature of the genome restricts further evolutionary developments. Eukaryotes, much developed than prokaryotes are specialized in photosynthesis and aerobic life with multiplicities of structures and activities.

The nucleus of eukaryotic cell contains two chromosomes from each of the two parents. Mitosis (nuclear division) results in,

- (i) the accurate replication of the genetic material (chromosomes) and
- (ii) the equal distribution of the chromosomes to the two daughter cell.

Living processes like earth's crust are also thoroughly associated with microbial processes. Microorganisms mainly prokaryotes with associated enzymes play important roles in the disintegration and deposition or absorption of minerals both on earth and in human or animal body systems⁶⁰.

Biogeochemical conversions are known to be associated not only with the deposition of coal, petroleum, natural gas, bauxite, silica but also with mineralization, solubilization, mobilization and immobilization of minerals and natural resources on earth and in human or animal body⁶⁰.

The basic biochemistry appears to be similar. All living process extant today have gone through a common evolutionary pathway.

Eukaryotes are specialized in photosynthesis and aerobic life with multiplication of structures and activities but prokaryotes are specialized in ecological functions like nitrogen fixation, nitrification, denitrification, sulfur and metal oxidation, methane formation etc.

Prokaryotes developed on their own but eukaryotes were always with prokaryotes. Eukaryotes afforded new ecological niches to prokaryotes. They protect prokaryotes and also served as prey⁶⁰.

Prokaryotes are very aggressive in nature which is the reason for highly developed defence, protection and survival mechanism of eukaryotes.

Similarly, mineralization or demineralization of compounds i.e. minerals as well as demineralization or depletion of minerals and elements in biological systems are carried out by prokaryotes (e.g. Ca-mobilization or depletion of Ca^{2+} in bones and bone marrows of human body are probably due to prokaryotes).

It is therefore, desirable to throw light on human microbiomics to understand the working of microbes in a living system.

Human microbiomics^{65,66} :

The unravelling of the mysteries of the human

microbiomics and their decoding are still a far cry. Microbes or bacteria (prokaryotes, eukaryotes and fungi) are essential components of each and every microscopic and macroscopic part of human body. The microbes are vital for human health and prevent dangerous microbes from establishing a foothold. At least 40–60% or even more human associated microbiomic, depending on the body sites, are not known. Naturally, their impact on their biological body system and their biodiversity are unaccountable.

The salient features are :

- (i) Bacteria or microbes far outnumber (by at least 10–100 times more) the cell (3×10^{13} cells) in human biosystem.
- (ii) Prokaryotic microbes far outnumber eukaryotic microbes in human body.
- (iii) Enormity of microbes in a human system with metabolic diversities and mutations cannot be cultured in the laboratory for proper experimental studies which eliminate the scope of understanding microbial diversities (beneficial or detrimental properties) and their effects.
- (iv) Microbes and micro enzymes are strictly specific with specific activities and specific microhabitats. There are likely to be a number of specific microbes with their own activity in any microhabitat.
- (v) Microbes and enzymes in diverse habitats in a body with diverse biochemical activities convert various organic and inorganic compounds (foods) into a wide range of metabolic products for sustaining the human or animal activities. There are countless biochemical transformations that are mediated by microbial genome which eliminates the scope of understanding the microbial diversities affecting the human systems.

Theories of carcinogenesis (cancer formation) in a human system :

Innumerable theories have been advanced for the development of oncogenesis in human or animal systems and the positive answer is illusive though the true answer for unfolding the genesis of the illusive disease ‘cancer’ beckons every oncologist.

The article presents a heuristic approach on the part of a physical chemist to induce the oncologists to examine and explore the non-conventional approach for cancer as well as for other critical diseases like AIDS, haemophilia, thalassemia. The reasons for oncogenesis are numerous. There may be related to oncogenic viruses, infections or to other reasons which may contribute to the development of human tumors by a number of mechanisms. Few of these are :

- (a) By inducing immunosuppression or by modifying the host cell genome without persistence of viral DNA.
- (b) Directly by inducing oncoproteins or by altering the expression of host cell proteins at the site of viral DNA integration.
- (c) Depression or oxidative stress (over load of harmful molecules called oxygen free radicals generated in the body) for a long spell.
- (d) Consumption of tobacco products. According to Hausen, viruses are considered to be the second most important risk factor for cancer development in humans, exceeded only by tobacco consumption⁶⁷.

The reasons may be important but secondary in nature. According to Vogelstein and Tomasetti⁶⁸, chances of cancer depends on the frequency of division of stem cells and the greater the division greater the risk of cancer causing mutation in a daughter cell. According to them, tissues that host the greater number of stem cell divisions are those most vulnerable to cancer. The authors claim that the theory explained two-thirds of all cancers. It is not certain whether cancer is due to environmental factor or due to genetic factors.

However, the analysis of the results from a large number studies suggests that most cancer cases are the result of biological bad luck and cancer often cannot be prevented⁶⁹.

However, it is always the efforts of man and scientists to overcome the “bad luck” and conquer the invincible “Cancer” by their strong determination, endless efforts and collective contributions to understand the reasons for the genesis of cancer and find ways and means for the prevention of cancer and curing cancer just like any other disease.

All the observations given before are but prelude for the presentation of 'Non-conventional theory' for oncogenesis.

Non-conventional theory of oncogenesis :

Viruses that produce tumors in their natural body or in experimental animals or induce malignant transformations of cells on culture are known as oncogenic viruses. Transformation (total or partial) is a multistep process like transformation, transduction, conjugation and cell-cell fusion for conversion of natural cells to malignant cells. Oncogenic viruses are classified according to nucleic acid content of the genome.

In reality, there is no specific oncogenic virus as such which covers all types of carcinogenesis in different parts of human organs and cancer cannot be regarded to be virus related diseases in the true sense of the term.

However, body is a biological ecosystem interwoven intimately with a large number of macroscopic with innumerable microscopic ecosystems or microhabitats or microbial niches having diverging characteristics.

These macro and micro environments are habitats of a large number of microbes (eukaryotes and prokaryotes with food, nutrients, fungi etc.). Each habitat has specific microbes with specific functions and contributions. These work collectively and synchronously to keep the normal health of any animal or human body. All the microbes (though different in nature) together with water and oxygen work independently but collectively as a whole as per schedule. Slight aberrations due to fever, diarrhoea, infections like pox, influenza etc. may cause disturbances but the healing mechanisms of the body (together with rest, medical supplements and nutrients) revert the system to their normal conditions depending on the extent of damage in the system. Aberration usually occur in a particular segment or microhabitat of the body containing specific microbes. However, if the aberrations are aggravated or accentuated by infections like pox or by inflammations, prolonged ulcerations, haemorrhages like oncogenic spots, the situation becomes abnormal or serious. The microbes prefer and invade active oncogenic spots having sufficient food and nutrients. Oncogenic spots are perfect 'chemostats' for the growth of bacteria i.e. eukaryotes and greater number of prokaryotes with favourable conditions like 37 °C and pH 7–8.5. Initially

microbes secrete depolymerase by which polysaccharides, proteins, nucleic acids are expected to be hydrolysed and accessible to the microbes. Aerobes rapidly consume oxygen and render the habitat anaerobic suitable for the growth of anaerobes or prokaryotes. Prokaryotes are very aggressive and multiply rapidly at the expense of host cells utilizing foods, nutrients, vitamins etc. in the microenvironments. The water content of the bacterial cells lies between 70–86%. Prokaryotes though anaerobes, require huge amount of water and oxygen for their rapid multiplication as they form the essential constituents of the microbial cells generated.

Usually prokaryotes derive oxygen from oxygen containing salts and foods but due to extensive aerobic processes and rapid multiplication of microbes, the oxygen deficient system derive oxygen from the decomposition of water molecules present in the micro environment and also from normal host cells. The onset of water decomposition appears to be most crucial stage. Rapid utilization of water not only destroys the H₂O-balance in the microsystem and neighbouring host cells but destroys the tetrahedral structure of water associated with structural changes of proteins, DNA, RNA which may even destroy the water on the surface of protein molecules. It is to be noted that the nature of the microbial activities and the nature of controlling metabolic fluxes are completely different at the oxic-anoxic interfaces⁷⁰. Enzymic activities of the affected cells are disturbed.

Water is the key for most of the biological functions of proteins, DNA, RNA, enzymes i.e. the biological functions of the body water is the integral part of protein-protein, protein-DNA, and protein ligand interactions aiding the natural recognition and processing genetic informations. Water also changes hydration and conformations of nucleic acid. It is probably associated with the universal process of information transfer in DNA replications, transcription and translation.

Changes of water structure and other biological molecules also changes ICF and ECF balance of the electrolytes leading to blood pressure and other associated complications. All the biological functions get disturbed.

Prokaryotes utilize the host cells for their rapid reproduction and cell division just like viruses. But prokaryotes, unlike viruses, are independent organisms and are haploids. Cell division of prokaryotes is preceded by transient conversion of haploid to diploid stage by doubling and replicating bacterial chromosomes. But prokaryotes utilize the chromosome of the host cells causing rapid and more vigorous multiplications of cells than those of viruses i.e. prokaryotes now act as strong viruses and infections aggravate their activities. Prokaryotes may come in contact with virus infected or other infected host cells to form bacteriophages. Prokaryotes or bacteriophage use normal cells just like in the nutrient culture media. They multiply, grow and proliferate on the surface of normal cells and ultimately the cells make contact with each other i.e. contact inhibition occurs. The result is the single layer of constant growth i.e. growing into several layers. The behavior is closely akin to the behavior of viruses.

In human and animal body the uncontrolled proliferation of cells produces tumors. If the body can contain and encapsulate their growth, they are called benign tumors.

However, if they grow without inhibition or interruption and invade the neighbouring and other cells to cause metastasis, malignant tumor or cancer occurs. It is to be noted that DNA contains the genetic information of cells, its replication and division always precedes cell division and lead to the formation of completely identical chromosome. However, the multiplication of prokaryotes acting as virus in the host cell must be a complicated process. Due to destruction or alteration of the structure of water molecules, structure of proteins, DNA, RNA etc. are likely to be altered. Thus the malignant growth should be hap-hazard in nature. Alignment of two double strands of DNA will be broken and rejoined crosswise but alignment may differ. But whatever may be the reasons or ways of formation of malignant tumors all are related to DNA, the hereditary material.

Due to abnormal microbial changes in the body, all normal functions of the affected micro and macro environments are disrupted. Infected prokaryotes cells invade and squeeze the neighbouring cells and there is gradual disruption of the metabolic and other functions of the body causing enormous suffering of the patient and ultimate collapse.

It should be realized that the basic human microbiomics are yet to be known properly and most of the microbes in the different microhabitats are yet to be cultured and cultivated in the laboratory for experimental details.

However, cancer formation is an irreversible process and is very difficult to be contained except at the early stages.

The seeds of cancer are not extraneous but are in our body systems. Cancer can be developed unknowingly and silently due to adverse intraneous conditions and cancer formation may thus be regarded to be 'due to bad luck'⁶⁹.

But science will move forward as 'Nothing is so fatal to the progress of the human mind as to suppose that our views of science are ultimate, that there are no mysteries in nature, that our triumphs are complete and there are no worlds to conquer'

Sir Humphrey Davy

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